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GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING NEEDS FOR SUSTAINABLE CAREER DECISION MAKING AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated the guidance and counselling needs for career decision making among senior secondary students in Abuja, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design. A sample size of 200 students was drawn from a population of 300 Senior Secondary School three (SS3) classes of four public secondary schools in four Area Councils of Abuja. The sample was randomly drawn for the study using simple random sampling technique. Questionnaire was designed and used by the researcher to elicit information on the career aspiration by the Senior Secondary School students. Twenty (20) professional counsellors were drawn from the four area council in Abuja for the pilot test in order to avoid unreliability. The researcher used Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to determine the reliability index of 0.83. Mean was used to answer the research questions. The findings revealed among others that, the adequate guideline to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decision making in life include: knowledge about requisite qualification, personality traits & qualities, rules and regulation guiding the conduct of the vocation, security, and hazard management. Based on the findings, recommendations were made.

Keywords: Guidance and Counselling, Career Decision, Students.

Introduction

Guidance and Counselling involve processes geared towards helping an individual understand himself and his social environment, so as to enable him make wise decisions in life and as well, have self-direction. In choosing a career, it is important to know how students develop their preferences. Parents, teachers and professional counsellors may be familiar with the major factors that influence vocational development of the individuals in making career decisions and finding the best probable match of a person with a particular class of work. Most senior students are ignorant of what appropriate career decision making is all about. All they seem to know are the subjects that made up the arts, social sciences, physical and biological sciences without knowing that, it takes more than these for appropriate career decision making to be developed. It would not be an overstatement to state that the most bugging problem facing the senior students of this country is the problem of unemployment. This problem does not allow our qualified youths to be employed after having completed their training. Makinde, Adeyefu and Adamolekun (2000) are of the view after exposure of youngsters to vital and wide information that, they would find value in what they are going in for. Youngsters make mistakes in their career decision making if they are not adequately briefed on the advantages and disadvantages of each career. Anyone provided with adequate information will be in better position to choose more wisely than a person without adequate information. Youngsters make mistake in their career

decision makings, because they are not appropriately guided. Therefore, senior students in secondary schools need appropriate career guidance and information in the selection of their careers in life, so that they would be useful to themselves and to the society. These would enable them to avoid possible frustration later in life.

Career guidance aims at helping, assisting, directing, guiding, stimulating and piloting the senior students to see the meaning in career, which they want to select (Okonkwo, 2007). Senior students while in schools need appropriate career guidance in their environment to be empowered in educational and career decision-making. Career can be defined as the totality of work one does in his lifetime. In other words career includes a number of occupations, vocations or jobs an individual engages in during his/her working life. Career is the sequence of major positions occupied by person throughout his pre-occupational and post occupational life, including work related roles such as those of a student, employee and pensioner, together with complementary vocational family and civic roles (Shertzer & Stone, 1981). Oni (1999) defines career education as a programme, which endeavours through the regular school curriculum to provide all youths in the school with motivation towards the world. Such education should consist of orientation to the nation's job opportunities available, and exploration of occupations consistent with student interest and abilities, which he benefit from and plan for pre-professional institution or vocational technical education. Onyemerekeya (2014) defines career guidance as a process of assisting a student match his personal characteristics, attributes, abilities, capabilities, interests, values, aptitudes and other personality characteristics in relation to the world of work.

Career guidance is a process of helping a person to match his personal attributes and his background with suitable jobs and employment opportunities. Akinade (2004) defines guidance as a set of cognitively oriented services designed to help individuals achieve certain goals. Akinade, Sokan and Osarenren (1999) define counselling as a more open and less directive method of helping in which alternatives are laid open before the client and the final decision is left for him/her to take. Career guidance can be described as a process of presenting in a well-structured manner, useful information, ideas or knowledge to individuals who can use such beneficially. Okonkwo (2007) opines that, guidance points towards helping, aiding, directing or assisting an individual towards better understanding of himself, and his world, which leads to proper adjustment for individual growth and societal development. Proper guidance and counselling assist individuals in career decision making process.

Career decision-making is one of the most difficult decisions in a person's life, yet it involves a person's total life as it determines his income, decision makings for friendships, pattern of dressing and very often, the amount of risk to which he is exposed. This period is very stressful, because it is the time when senior students strive to meet most of the developmental, task. It is obvious that most parents are illiterate and ignorant of all the senior students' problems (Okonkwo, 2009).

It is against this background that the researchers view the uncertainty of the adolescent's future problems concerning their career guidance and career decision makings. The researchers thought it wise to search and identify the appropriate information/guidelines that should be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decision, identify the factors that will influence appropriate career decision making, and why there is need for appropriate career decision making.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this paper is to investigate the guidance and counselling needs for career decision making among senior secondary students in Abuja, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. find out the adequate guidelines needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life;
2. ascertain the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students; and
3. examine the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja.

Research Questions

Three research questions guided the study.

1. What are the adequate guideline needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life?
2. What are the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students?
3. What are the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja?

Methodology

The design for this study is ex-post facto. The population comprised 300 Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja, FCT having 3,769 SS3 students and 320 professional counsellors. A sample of Forty (40) professional counsellors was drawn using simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was researcher's designed questionnaire titled 'Guidance and Counselling Needs for Career Decision Making Questionnaire (GCNCDMQ). The questionnaire was structured on a modified Likert's scale of four-point ratings. A draft copy of the questionnaire was validated by two (2) experts in Guidance and Counselling Department. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test-retest method. This was done within two weeks interval and the two separate scores obtained were correlated using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, which yielded an index of 0.83. Mean and rank order statistics were used to answer the research questions.

Result

Research Question One: What are the adequate guideline needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life?

Table 1: Mean scores of counsellors on adequate guideline needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life

S/N	Items	Mean Scores	Rank Order	Decision
1.	Students need adequate guidelines on the subjects to be taken for future career growth	3.04	9th	Agree
2.	The subjects must be adequate for the degree courses they want at tertiary level	3.13	3rd	Agree
3.	They need to be guided on courses that give them immediate employment after graduation	3.08	6th	Agree
4.	They are to be guided to possess entrepreneurial skills during and after graduation	3.11	4th	Agree
5.	Guiding them to be creative in taking career decisions	3.22	2 nd	Agree
6.	Helping them to be innovative in their daily tasks for future growth	3.09	5 th	Agree
7.	Guiding them to be more security conscious in life for safety reasons	3.01	10 th	Agree
8.	Assisting them to possess knowledge of hazard management policies at work-place	3.06	7 th	Agree
9.	Grooming them to possess proper time management skills while on job	3.25	1 st	Agree

10.	Guiding them to possess the skill of communication networking while on job	3.00	11 th	Agree
11.	Establishing them with the application of health management practices during and after graduation	3.05	8 th	Agree

Table 1 presents the mean scores of counsellors on the adequate guideline needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life. The respondents agreed on all the items in the table with high mean scores ranging from 1st to 11th on the order of ranking. The guidelines needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life include: guiding them on the subjects to be taken for future career growth, taking subjects that are adequate for the degree courses they want at tertiary level, guiding them on courses that can give them immediate employment after graduation, guiding them to possess entrepreneurial skills during and after graduation, guiding them be creative in taking career decisions, helping them to be innovative in their daily tasks for future growth, guiding them to be more security conscious in life for safety reasons, assisting them to possess knowledge of hazard management policies at work-place, grooming them to possess proper time management skills while on job, guiding them to possess the skill of communication networking while on job, and establishing them with the application of health management practices during and after graduation.

Research Question Two: What are the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students?

Table 2: Mean scores of counsellors on the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students

S/N	Items	Mean Scores	Rank Order	Decision
12	Interest	3.03	8th	Agree
13	Intelligence	3.01	9th	Agree
14	Aptitude	3.00	10th	Agree
15	Personality	3.05	6th	Agree
16	Self-concept	3.08	5th	Agree
17	Home/family	3.21	1st	Agree
18	Value of society	3.13	2nd	Agree
19	Subject combination	3.09	4th	Agree
20	Influence of school	3.12	3rd	Agree
21	Religious factor	3.04	7th	Agree

Table 2 presents the mean scores of counsellors on the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students. The respondents agreed on all the items in the table with high mean scores ranging from 1st to 10th on the order of ranking. The factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students include: interest, intelligence, aptitude, personality, self-concept, home/family, value of society, subject combination, school influence, and religious factor.

Research Question Three: What are the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja?

Table 3: Mean scores of counsellors on the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja

S/ N	Items	Mean Scores	Rank Order	Decisi on
1.	Increasing general knowledge among students	3.05	7th	Agree
2.	Creating self -awareness among students	3.03	8th	Agree
3.	Helping students choose appropriate career	3.12	4th	Agree
4.	Widening and strengthening the career horizons of senior students	3.15	3rd	Agree
5.	Assisting senior students in the development of right attitudes to work	3.09	6th	Agree
6.	Uncovering hidden talents and traits among senior students	3.11	5th	Agree
7.	Avoiding unemployment among school leavers	3.16	2nd	Agree
8.	Equipping the students with prerequisite skills needed to gain employment after school	3.25	1st	Agree

Table 3 presents the mean scores of counsellors on the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja. The respondents agreed on all the items in the table with high mean scores ranging from 1st to 8th on the order of ranking. The needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja include: increasing general knowledge among students, creating self -awareness among students, helping students choose appropriate career, widening and strengthening the career horizons of senior students, assisting senior students in the development of right attitudes to work, Uncovering hidden talents and traits among senior students, avoiding unemployment among school leavers, and equipping the students with prerequisite skills needed to gain employment after school.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that, the guidelines needed to be given to senior students to enable them make appropriate career decisions in life include: guiding them on the subjects to be taken for future career growth, taking subjects that are adequate for the degree courses they want at tertiary level, guiding them on courses that can give them immediate employment after graduation, guiding them to possess entrepreneurial skills during and after graduation, guiding them be creative in taking career decisions, helping them to be innovative in their daily tasks for future growth, guiding them to be more security conscious in life for safety reasons, assisting them to possess knowledge of hazard management policies at work-place, grooming them to possess proper time management skills while on job, guiding them to possess the skill of communication networking while on job, and establishing them with the application of health management practices during and after graduation. This finding agrees with that of Makinde, Adeyefu and Ademalokun (2014), which stated that after exposure of youngsters to vital and wide information, they will find value in what they are going in for. Also, that youngster makes mistakes in their career decision making, if they are not d guided on the advantages and disadvantages of each career. Therefore, everybody needs to be provided with adequate information. Senior students in secondary schools need appropriate career guidance and information in the selection of their careers for

sustainable future, so that they would be useful to themselves, family and the larger society.

The findings of this study further revealed that, the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students include: interest, intelligence, aptitude, personality, self-concept, home/family, value of society, subject combination, school influence, and religious factor. This finding equally with that of Ogbodo (2015) that, senior secondary school students need career guidance and to match with their personality for their future career purposes. This is the time when senior students strive to meet their developmental tasks, yet most parents are illiterates and ignorant of all the senior students problems. This result has portrayed that, there are many problems influencing appropriate career decision making among senior students for future growth.

The findings of this study finally revealed that, the needs for appropriate career decision making in the lives of students in senior secondary schools in Abuja include: increasing general knowledge among students, creating self-awareness among students, helping students choose appropriate career, widening and strengthening the career horizons of senior students, assisting senior students in the development of right attitudes to work, Uncovering hidden talents and traits among senior students, avoiding unemployment among school leavers, and equipping the students with prerequisite skills needed to gain employment after school. In line with the finding, Onyemereke (2010) sees career guidance as a process of assisting a student match his personal characteristics, and attributes, capabilities, interests, values, aptitudes and others. Therefore, there are many reasons why senior students in secondary schools need appropriate career decision making for sustainable living.

Conclusion

The study concluded that counsellors need to give senior students proper guidelines enable them make appropriate career decisions in life. Interest, intelligence, aptitude, personality, self-concept, home/family, value of society, subject combination, school influence, and religious factor are the factors influencing appropriate career decision making in the lives of senior students. Senior secondary school students must make appropriate career decisions for sustainable future.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. School counsellors should give senior students proper guidelines in subjects' selections to enable them choose better courses at tertiary level and make appropriate career decisions in life.
2. School counsellors should assist to develop positive influence on the students and direct them for appropriate decisions about their choice of courses for growth.
3. Senior secondary school students should equally be involved in taking decisions about their choice of subjects for individual growth and sustainable future.
4. Counsellors should be able to assist the senior students to grow and realize their full potentials in developing realistic career plans based on the knowledge of self and requirements in the world of work.

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